

Controlled Synthesis of Iron Oxide Nanoparticles over a Wide Size Range

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Abstract- We report on the effect of using decanoic acid as capping ligand on the synthesis of iron oxide nanoparticles by thermal decomposition of an organic iron precursor in organic medium. This procedure allowed us to control the particle size within 5 nm and about 30 nm by modifying the precursor-to-capping ligand ratio in a systematic fashion and to further expand the particle size range up to about 50 nm by adjusting the final synthesis temperature. The nanoparticles also showed high saturation magnetization of about 80-83 emu/g at low temperature, almost size-independent and close to the value for the bulk counterpart. Decanoic acid-coated nanoparticles were transferred to water by using tetramethylammonium hydroxide, which allowed further coating with silica in a tetraethyl orthosilicate solution. Consequently, these iron oxide nanoparticles are tunable in size and highly magnetic, and they could become suitable candidates for various biomedical applications such as contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging and magnetic carriers for drug delivery.

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Introduction

Magnetic nanoparticles (MNP) are attracting renewed interest, mainly due to their promising applications in biomedicine and nonlinear optics.¹⁻³ As the size is reduced, the magnetic structure at the

surface layer differs from that of the particle core, giving rise to remarkable effects on the magnetic ordering within the whole particle.^{4,5} Consequently, understanding and controlling the effects of surface chemistry on the magnetic properties have become increasingly important issues for many technological applications of MNP, such as high-density magnetic storage, magnetic resonance imaging, and drug delivery.

The use of MNP in biomedical applications may bring about significant advances in diagnosis, prevention, and treatment of diseases.⁶ The potential application of MNP for biomedical purposes relies on the synthesis of high-quality materials, mainly regarding crystallinity and magnetic response. In this respect, it is essential to minimize the polydispersity and heterogeneity of the particles and to maximize their magnetic response. For instance, MNP for drug delivery and contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging must exhibit a high magnetic response to external fields and should have functionalized, biocompatible surfaces.^{7,8} However, the synthesis of such MNP is, in general, a critical issue since the properties of each specific sample depend on several parameters in a complex manner. Deeper understanding of these complex effects is necessary to design and control new synthesis methods yielding high-quality MNP. In this respect, some mechanisms have been recently reported that may enable the synthesis of such kind of particles.⁹

Syntheses based on the decomposition of organometallic precursors have proven successful for the preparation of monodisperse nanoparticles.¹⁰⁻¹⁴ In particular, the synthesis of iron oxide nanoparticles (magnetite/maghemite $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) by thermal decomposition of an organic iron precursor in a high boiling point organic solvent yields highly crystalline MNP with excellent magnetic properties.^{15, 16} Typically, this method was limited to a maximum particle size of about 20-30 nm¹². However, some recent works have been published regarding morphology control,¹⁷⁻¹⁹ and very recently Hyeon and co-workers have reported the synthesis of MNP in a new size range up to around 160 nm, using oleic acid as capping ligand and by modifying the standard procedure²⁰. Besides, the synthesis of iron oxide MNP by coprecipitation also enables reaching a wide range of sizes, but the obtained particles show lower magnetic response as compared to those obtained from thermal decomposition and a marked tendency to agglomerate in the range of sizes suitable for most biomedical applications.²¹ Therefore, it is essential to develop new synthetic routes, based on the decomposition of organometallic precursors, in order to control the range of achievable particle sizes without significant deterioration of their magnetic properties.

The decomposition of iron(III) acetylacetonate in dibenzyl ether in the presence of oleic acid has been used to synthesize monodisperse iron oxide nanoparticles. However, tuning of particle size typically requires the use of several solvents and may be achieved by modifying the amount of solvent, heating profile, and/or reaction time¹². However the systematic study of the influence of each of those parameters has not been performed, yet. In this work, we have expanded on the use of the thermal

decomposition method ¹⁴ by studying the influence of decanoic acid as a capping ligand. We have studied in detail the effect of modifying the molar ratio of iron(III) acetylacetonate-to-decanoic acid on the resulting particle shape and size. The use of decanoic acid as capping ligand while the solvent remains the same as been found to enable the preparation of cubic-shaped iron oxide MNP with sizes ranging from 5 nm up to about 30 nm, while exhibiting magnetic properties which are very close to that of bulk magnetite. Furthermore, the range of sizes may be further expanded up to about 50 nm just by adjusting the final synthesis temperature. This new synthesis approach thus constitutes a powerful method since it yields MNP of tunable size and high magnetic response.

Experimental Section

The synthesis in this work is a modification of a method previously reported. Iron(III) acetylacetonate (99%), decanoic acid (98%), and dibenzyl ether (98%) were purchased from Across. NH₄OH (33 wt % in water) and tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) (98%) was purchased from Aldrich. All chemicals were used as received. Pure grade ethanol, isopropanol and Milli-Q grade water were used to make up the solutions.

5 nm Particles: To synthesize iron oxide cube-octahedral-shaped nanoparticles of about 5 nm in edge length (see Figure 1a), 0.353 g (1 mmol) of iron(III) acetylacetonate was mixed with 1.033 g (6 mmol) of decanoic acid in 25 mL of dibenzyl ether. The iron(III) acetylacetonate-to-decanoic acid molar ratio was 1:6. First, the solution was heated up to 200 °C with a constant heating rate of 6-7 °C/min under an argon blanket flow and vigorous stirring. After 2 h at 200 °C, the solution was heated up to reflux and kept at this temperature for 1 h. Finally, the solution was cooled down to room temperature, washed several times with a mixture of hexane and ethanol at a concentration of 1:2, and collected by centrifugation at 8000 rpm.

12 nm Particles: To synthesize iron oxide nanocubes of about 12 nm in edge length (see Figure 1b), 0.353 g (1 mmol) of iron(III) acetylacetonate was mixed with 0.861 g (5 mmol) of decanoic acid in 25 mL of dibenzyl ether (Figure 1b). As for 5 nm particles, after heating up to 200 °C and staying at this temperature for 2 h, the solution was heated to reflux and maintained at this temperature for 1 h. After cooling down to room temperature, the particles were collected by centrifugation at 8000 rpm and washed several times with a mixture of hexane and ethanol. The iron(III) acetylacetonate-to-decanoic acid molar ratio was 1:5.

20 nm Particles: Larger nanocubes of about 20 nm in edge length (see Figure 1c) were obtained by increasing the molar ratio between the iron(III) acetylacetonate and decanoic acid to 1:4; 0.353 g (1 mmol) of iron(III) acetylacetonate was mixed with 0.688 g (4 mmol) of decanoic acid in 25 mL of dibenzyl ether. Following the same procedure as that used to obtain smaller sizes, the solution was heated up to 200 °C under an argon flow and vigorous stirring and kept at this temperature for 2 h. In a second step, the solution was heated up to reflux temperature and was maintained at this temperature for

1 h. Then, the solution was cooled down to room temperature. In this case, the washing procedure used to collect the particles was slightly different. First, the particles were precipitated by centrifugation at 8500 rpm of the as prepared mixture without adding any extra solvent. Second, collected particles were washed with a mixture of hexane and acetone.

26 nm Particles: The largest particles of 26 nm in size length (see Figure 1d) were synthesized by mixing 0.353 g (1 mmol) of iron(III) acetylacetonate and 0.517 g (3 mmol) of decanoic acid in 25 mL of dibenzyl ether. The iron(III) acetylacetonate-to-decanoic acid molar ratio was 1:3. The synthesis procedure is the same as used in the other synthesis; the mixture was heated up with a heating rate of 6-7 °C/min to 200 °C and kept at this temperature for 2 h. Finally, the solution was heated up to reflux temperature and maintained at this temperature for 1 h. After cooling the mixture down to room temperature, particles were precipitated by centrifuging at 8000 rpm without the addition of any extra solvent. Then the collected particles were washed with a mixture of hexane and acetone.

30 and 46 nm Particles: Departing from an iron(III) acetylacetonate-to-decanoic acid molar ratio of 1:4, and following the same procedure as that for the 20 nm particles, the final synthesis temperatures were 275 and 265 °C, respectively, while the heating profile was exactly the same.

Phase Transfer to Water: Typically, 5 mL of a TMAOH 0.001 M solution in ethanol were added to 1 mL of a concentrated solution of nanoparticles in hexane. After sonication for 10 min, the solution was centrifuged three times in order to clean the excess of TMAOH. The particles were finally redispersed in Milli-Q water.

Silica Coating: After the phase transfer to water, 0.9 mL of water-soluble nanoparticles was added to 4 mL of ethanol, followed by the addition of 81.5 µL of NH₄OH and 6 µL of TEOS under mechanical stirring. The mixture was allowed to react for 6 h. Particles were precipitated with a magnet, washed with ethanol and twice with water.

Results and Discussion

Figure 1 shows some transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images of the as-synthesized iron oxide nanoparticles for different iron(III) acetylacetonate-to-decanoic acid molar ratios. For the smallest ratio (1:6), pseudospherical particles of about 5 nm in diameter were obtained, which tend to self-assemble into three-dimensional arrangements due to their high monodispersity (see Supporting Information). For intermediate molar ratios, such as 1:5 and 1:4, quasi-regular cubic-shaped particles of 12 and 20 nm in edge length, respectively, were obtained (see Figure 1b and 1c). Even larger cubic particles of 26 nm in edge length could be synthesized using a molar ratio of 1:3 (Figure 1d).

Figure 1 shows that the size of the nanoparticles decreases by increasing the relative concentration of decanoic acid (see Figure S2, S3, S4 and S5 in Supporting Information for a detailed TEM analysis as a

function of the molar ratio; Figure S6 shows the actual dependence of the mean edge length on the relative concentration of decanoic acid). A similar size dependence was previously observed when oleic acid was used as capping ligand instead of decanoic acid. However, in that case, the maximum variation observed in the particle size as a function of the precursor-to-surfactant ratio was less than 20%^{22, 23} when the rest of parameters (solvent, heating profile, reaction time, etc.) were maintained fixed. It should also be pointed out that the particles larger than 10 nm showed cubic shape when they were synthesized in the presence of decanoic acid as capping ligand.

Figure 1. TEM micrographs of iron oxide nanoparticles with average edge length of (a) 5 nm, (b) 12 nm, (c) 20 nm and (d) 26 nm.

High-resolution TEM (HRTEM) evidenced the high crystallinity of all the samples (see Figures S7-S9 in the Supporting Information for all particle sizes). For example, Figure 2a shows the HRTEM micrograph of a 20 nm particle where the lattice fringes correspond to the Bravais lattice planes. The Fourier transform of a selected area of the image -which is framed in Figure 2a with a red-dotted square yields a diffraction pattern that is shown in Figure 2b. This pattern can be indexed to the 100 zone axis of the iron oxide FCC spinel structure. Diffraction patterns do not allow us to distinguish between magnetite and maghemite structures. Figure 2c shows the reconstruction of the lattice within the selected area of the image in Figure 2a by inverse Fourier transform using only the indexed diffraction

spots in Figure 2b, which demonstrates the high crystalline quality of the particles. Electron diffraction patterns for all samples are also provided in the Supporting Information (see Figures S2-S5).

Figure 2. (a) HRTEM image of a 20 nm iron oxide nanoparticle, (b) Fourier transform of the selected area framed in (a); and (c) reconstruction of the lattice by inverse Fourier transformation using only indexed diffraction spots in (b).

Figure 3 shows the magnetization hysteresis loop at 5 K as a function of the mean particle size. In the high field regime, the magnetization curves $M(H)$ can be fitted to $M(H) = M_s + \chi_d H$, M_s being the zero-field saturation magnetization and χ_d the high-field differential susceptibility that accounts for the surface spin disorder.²⁴⁻²⁷ M_s ranges from 80 to 83 emu/g (see Table 1 in the Supporting Information), values which are close to that corresponding to bulk magnetite (98 emu/g)²⁸ and almost size independent as reported elsewhere^{15, 29-31} This high value of M_s is in contrast with those of iron oxide nanoparticles of similar sizes synthesized by coprecipitation methods, which are much lower.^{32, 33} Magnetic parameters of particles obtained by coprecipitation methods are also strongly size-dependent, and bulk values are only recovered for sizes above 100-150 nm.³³ However, for particles synthesized by decomposition of an organic precursor in the presence of oleic acid, similarly high values of the saturation magnetization have been previously reported.^{15, 16, 20}

In the latter, saturation magnetization at 5 K did not show any significant dependence on the particle size as is also the case for the particles in this work. The values of χ_d for particles synthesized by coprecipitation methods are also 2 orders of magnitude higher than those found in iron oxide particles synthesized by decomposition methods in the presence of both decanoic and oleic acids. This is

tentatively attributed to the lower spin disorder at the particle surface. This is also in agreement with the high particle crystallinity, even observed at the particle surface, as shown in Figure 2a. The crystallinity of the particles, arising from the high-temperature synthesis, has been claimed to be one of the crucial parameters to obtain high-quality magnetic nanoparticles, as compared to those synthesized by low-temperature coprecipitation methods.^{15, 16, 20} Zero field and field cooling magnetization curves as a function of temperature are shown in Figure S10 of the Supporting Information. It is worth noting that only the particles of 5 nm in size have a blocking temperature below room temperature, as expected taking into account both the volume of the iron oxide nanoparticles and the magnetic anisotropy of iron oxides. The 5 nm particles are indeed superparamagnetic at room temperature.

Figure 3. Magnetization hysteresis loop at 5 K for the iron oxide nanoparticles as a function of the mean particle size. Inset: detail of the low magnetic field region.

The relatively wide range of particle sizes that can be obtained via this one-pot process with decanoic acid may be related to subtle differences in the thermodynamic aspects of the reaction. The boiling point of oleic acid (360 °C) is far above those of the solvents typically used in the synthesis, such as dibenzyl ether (298 °C), octyl ether (285 °C), or octadecene (315 °C) and close to trioctylamine (365 °C).^{12, 14, 34} In contrast, the boiling point of decanoic acid (268 °C) is well below the boiling temperature of those solvents, and in particular this is the present case since dibenzyl ether was used in our work.^{35, 36} Thus,

the mechanisms of particle nucleation and growth may be quite different as compared to the case of oleic acid. Different experiments were performed at temperatures below the reflux temperature of the solvent while keeping constant the heating rate. For temperatures below 250 °C no particles were formed, whereas only for temperatures higher than 260 °C particles were obtained (see Figure S11 in the Supporting Information). In this case, the particles present a broader size distribution, more irregular shape, and bigger sizes than those expected for higher synthesis temperatures. In addition, the average size decreases as the synthesis temperature increases, pointing toward a temperature-dependent decomposition of the Fe(III) precursor. For a Fe(III):decanoic acid fixed molar ratio of 1:4, particles with average sizes of 20 ± 5 nm, 30 ± 10 nm and 48 ± 20 nm were obtained when working at reflux, 275 °C, and 265 °C, respectively (see Figure S11 in the Supporting Information). Consequently, the use of decanoic acid as new capping ligand allows the synthesis of high quality crystallographic and magnetic Fe_{3-x}O₄ nanoparticles with particles size ranging within 5 and 50 nm by controlling the molar ratio and final synthesis temperature. It should also be pointed out that the presence of oleic acid for the same synthesis conditions only yields particles when the synthesis temperatures are close to the reflux temperature and the obtained sizes range does not change significantly as a function of the final temperature.

In order to elucidate the mechanism leading to the formation of iron oxide particles, Fourier transform infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) experiments were performed at five different stages of the reaction (see Figures S13 and S14 in the Supporting Information). The iron(III) acetylacetonate-to-decanoic acid molar ratio was 1:6, while the molar ratio of dibenzyl ether-to-decanoic acid was reduced to 1:1 in order to obtain an optimum FT-IR signal for the reagents. As the reaction evolves, the FT-IR spectra clearly indicate that the iron(III) acetylacetonate decomposes, which is evidenced by the decreasing of the absorption peaks at 1576 and 1525 cm⁻¹ (Figure S13). Besides, the appearance of a bond between the decanoate ion and the NP surface is clearly shown in the FT-IR spectrum collected from the final dried NP after washing three times with acetone (see Figure S14 in the Supporting Information). The peaks within 1430 and 1597 cm⁻¹ correspond to the CO stretching due to the coordination of the decanoate ion with iron cations at the particle surface.³⁶

We aim at studying the formation of an intermediate iron complex during the synthesis process. Figure S13 shows that at 200 °C the organic iron precursor indeed decomposes, which should yield an intermediate iron complex, since no particle growing has been observed up to about 260 °C. However, FT-IR spectra are not conclusive about the existence of detectable amounts of an iron decanoate salt at the intermediate stages of the synthesis because of the superimposition of a broad peak (1510 - 1670 cm⁻¹) attributed to acetylacetonate, arising from the decomposition of iron(III) acetylacetonate.

On the other hand, an excess of decanoic acid may provoke the rapid coating of the available nuclei that prevents their further growing, favoring the stabilization of the nuclei. In contrast, a lower relative

concentration of decanoic leads to larger particles. In this case, lowering the amount of decanoic acid may promote a faster growth of the particles, thus resulting in a more unstable system, which would explain the broadening of the particle size distribution as the average size increases (see Figures S2-S5 in Supporting Information).

The absence of oleylamine also seems to be of relevance since the boiling point of this co-surfactant is higher than that of decanoic acid, as shown in some works that have used shorter fatty acids in the presence of oleylamine.³⁷ All in all, particle size can easily be tuned by changing the iron(III) acetylacetoante-to-decanoic acid molar ratio, such that smaller particles are obtained when the ratio is reduced.

The shape of the particles also seems to be dependent on the relative concentration of decanoic acid. With the smallest molar ratio of precursor-to-decanoic acid studied in this work (1:6), particles are quasi- spherical, while they become cubic for larger sizes as the relative concentration of decanoic acid is reduced. For intermediate molar ratios (1:4), Figure 1c shows that the particles present a pseudo-star-like shape that may be viewed as a precursor of the cubic shape. Increasing the molar ratio (1:3) makes the shape of the particles become more uniform and closer to cubic. The underlying synthesis mechanism could also be responsible for this shape evolution: a faster growth of the nuclei with decreasing molar fraction of decanoic acid could lead to a cubic shape, as this is the crystal symmetry of the unit cell.

Carrying out the synthesis in the presence of a fatty acid with a shorter carbon chain seems to give a more unstable system. As a result, a wide range of particle sizes and different particle shapes may be achieved by modifying solely the molar fraction between iron(III) acetylacetonate and decanoic acid.

Finally, it must also be mentioned that these decanoic acid-coated particles can be easily transferred into water by using tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAOH)³⁸ or other surfactants such as for example cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB).³⁹⁻⁴¹ The transfer to water additionally allows further silica coating of these particles. However, since the ferromagnetic nature of the bigger particles provides them with a high tendency to aggregate, interparticle magnetic interactions become smaller as the size decreases. Previous works by Philipse and co-workers showed that the formation of dipolar chains of nanoparticles in ferrofluids could be observed by cryogenic electron microscopy.⁴² Other methods have been developed by Pyun and co-workers where structures formed by interacting particles in solution could be “frozen” either by an *in situ* surface-polymerization process⁴³⁻⁴⁵ or by the so-called fossilized liquid assembly (FLA) method, yielding for example a chain-like assembly of cobalt nanoparticles.⁴⁶ In this work, chains of fossilized iron oxide nanoparticles were obtained through silica coating using slightly modified standard methods.^{47, 48} Although the coating of individual Co particles

covered by silica shell in dilute solution has already been reported,^{49, 50} Figure 4 shows that silica deposition may also lead to chain-like structures of iron oxide nanoparticles in which the chains formed in solution are fixed through slow silica precipitation forming a ca. 2 nm coating.

Figure 4. (a) Low and (b) high magnification TEM micrographs of ca. 2 nm silica coating of 12 nm iron oxide nanoparticles.

Conclusions

In this work, a novel method based on the decomposition of iron(III) acetylacetonate in the presence of decanoic acid as capping ligand, to synthesize iron oxide nanoparticles of tunable size from 5 to 50 nm in edge length, is reported. Tailoring the size of the particles is accomplished by modifying solely the iron(III) acetylacetonate-to-decanoic acid molar ratio. Particle size can be further expanded by controlling the final synthesis temperature. The particles are highly crystalline and tend to self-organize in large ordered aggregates. These nanoparticles can also be transferred to water and coated with silica shells. As a result, we suggest that they are appropriate for biomedical applications, such as contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging and drug delivery.

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Additional information, size distribution, ZFC-FC curves, IR absorption spectra, XRD, etc. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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